

“CALLED FOR THE OTHER”: THE UBUNTU PHILOSOPHY IN DIALOGUE WITH LEVINAS’ ETHICS OF RESPONSIBILITY

BY

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Abstract

This article argues that the principles and values of Ubuntu philosophy—closely aligned with Levinasian ethics of responsibility—are fundamental not only for the moral flourishing of society but also for its political and economic well-being. Despite the presence of these values in Tanzanian society, there is a continued experience of social challenges such as resentment, marriage breakdowns, and political instability. This apparent contradiction prompts a critical inquiry into the root causes of such issues. Using a qualitative analytic method, the article reveals that the mere presence or theoretical acknowledgment of Ubuntu and Levinasian ethical principles is insufficient to cultivate a harmonious society. The study finds that these values must be actively integrated, internalized, and concretized into everyday life. A key recommendation is the cultivation of an attitude of care and responsibility toward the other—beginning at the family level, where children must be raised with a mindset of love, empathy, and interconnectedness. Without such practical application and lived experience, Ubuntu values risk remaining abstract and ineffective. Therefore, for Ubuntu philosophy to have a tangible impact, its principles must be comprehended and practiced in a concretized, experiential manner, deeply embedded in the fabric of daily social interactions.

Key words: The “Other”, Ubuntu Philosophy, Ethics of Responsibility, the face of the Other.

Introduction

“A person is a person through other persons”—this foundational tenet of Ubuntu philosophy underscores a universal understanding of humanity that centers on relational existence. Similarly, Emmanuel Levinas, through his phenomenology of the Face, emphasizes the ethical imperative of “being for the Other,” where ethical responsibility emerges from encountering the Other’s face. Both philosophical frameworks—Ubuntu’s communal ethics and Levinas’ ethics of responsibility—converge on the idea that ethical living is not abstract, but rather a concrete experience rooted in everyday human interactions. This article explores a comparative analysis between Ubuntu philosophical thought and Levinasian ethics of responsibility, highlighting how both traditions emphasize relational

ethics and mutual responsibility. It argues that, if properly internalized, these frameworks can offer a

profound ethical vision capable of shaping a meaningful and morally grounded society. However, despite the presence of Ubuntu values in Tanzanian society, complemented by insights from Levinasian thought, persistent social issues—such as resentment, marital breakdowns, and political instability—continue to manifest. Using a qualitative analytic method, the article identifies the core problem: a failure to effectively integrate and internalize these ethical principles into concrete daily life. Rather than being lived out, these values often remain abstract—something Levinas himself cautions against. The article calls for a deliberate effort, particularly within families, to cultivate and practice these values from an early age. Parents play a critical role in instilling the culture of care, love, and responsibility in their children. Moreover, marital relationships must reflect these ethical commitments, as the family unit is central to the moral and social development of any society. Thus, the central question this article addresses is: What is the principal reason behind the failure of

Ubuntu principles and Levinasian ethics of responsibility to foster the intended social harmony in contemporary Tanzanian society?

1. Introducing Ubuntu Philosophy and Levinasian Ethics of Responsibility

Ubuntu, a term originating from the *Nguni Bantu* languages of Southern Africa, is a more than just a word. It refers to a philosophical concept that encapsulates the essence of humanity and communalism (Ajitoni, 2024: 1). The term is often translated as “I am because we are” emphasizing the interconnectedness and interdependence of individuals within a community (Ewuoso C, Hall S, 2019). The Ubuntu philosophy, highlights the notion that an individual’s identity and sense of self, are deeply rooted in their relationships with others and their contribution to the collective well-being of the community. It embraces the interconnectedness between humans and all creation, i.e. the relationship between people, the environment, and spirituality (Mbiti, 1969; Seehawer, 2023).

Historically, Ubuntu philosophy has been integral to African societies, guiding social interactions, governance, marriages and their conflict resolutions. It has served as a moral compass, promoting values such as empathy, compassion, respect, and mutual support (Fagunwa T, 2019). The core message of Ubuntu philosophy revolves around a simple truth: “one is because we are”, the notion that shows how each person’s destiny connects inseparably to everyone’s well-being. This implies that, the essence of Ubuntu, lies in the Nguni saying “*Umuntu Ngumuntu Ngabantu*” which indicates that people become truly human through their connections with others. This idea, reaches beyond simple social connections and shows that our identity depends on our community both casually and metaphysically. This philosophy then, teaches us that our personal well-being is tied to others’ welfare’ creating a web of mutual dependence that keeps social harmony alive (Bello, 2025). From this context, it is clearly observed that, by emphasizing the importance of community, shared values, and mutual support, the Ubuntu philosophy provides a framework for fostering social harmony and collective well-being in diverse contexts (Ajitoni, 2024: 2). Therefore, embarking on the discussion about the

Ubuntu philosophy in contemporary society, becomes crucial as it offers valuable insights and perspectives on addressing contemporary social and ethical challenges such as inequality, marital conflicts as well as social changes due to advancements in modern technologies (Msengana N. W, 2006).

In line with the spirit of Ubuntu philosophy, is the notion of Levinasian ethics of responsibility which like Ubuntu, delves deeply into the ethical relationship between the self and the Other. For Levinas, true ethical engagement arises from the encounter with the Other, emphasizing responsibility and asymmetrical over mere contractual or institutional arrangements. Levinas’ philosophy shifts the focus from individual autonomy to the ethical obligation that one has toward the Other.

Furthermore, the Levinasian ethics emphasizes the primacy of ethics over ontology, arguing that the face-to-face encounter with another person transcends not mere intellectual comprehension, but rather shifts the focus to the “ethical responsibility” derived from the encounter with the Other (Treanor, 2006:4). This relational dynamic proposed by Levinas, is not just a subset of human experience, but rather a very foundation of experience whereby each encounter with the face of the Other, invokes an infinite imperative to act ethically, transcending the confines of totality and creating an opening towards infinity. In meeting with the Other, one is called to an ethical responsibility that is immediate and profound. For Levinas, the face is not merely a physical or visual experience, rather; it is an encounter with another human being who commands moral consideration and respect. Therefore, for Levinas like Ubuntu, ethics is not merely a branch of philosophy concerned with abstract principles, but the first philosophy and the foundational way that we relate to one another. For the essential ethical moment for Levinas, occurs in the face-to-face encounter with another person. (Fagenblat, Erdur, 2020:258).

Levinas’ reorientation of philosophy towards ethics compels us to reconsider the primacy we place upon rationality, self-interest, and ontological concerns. And by asserting that ethics emanates from our encounters with the Other, Levinas provides robust grounds for a philosophy deeply attuned to human “vulnerability” and “responsibility”. Furthermore, Levinas’ ethical philosophy hinges on the concept of the “Other”

whereby the concept of the Other refers to another “human being who is profoundly different from oneself”. This Other is not just an entity or another object in the world but is a unique individual who commands “ethical responsibility.”(Fagenblat, Erdur, 2020:234). From this context, it is clearly observed that Levinas holds high the dignity of human Other, and for better than considering the Other as equal, Levinas recognizes the Other with much respect as above oneself. This indicates that, the explication of Levinas’ ethics of responsibility, highlights the noble aim for ethical peace, starting with one’s free and hospitable responsibility for other’s well-being (Levinas, 2023).

2. Principles and Values of Ubuntu Philosophy

Ubuntu philosophy, is founded on a set of core principles and values that emphasize, empathy, interconnectedness, relationality, collective responsibility and communal accountability, social justice, and recognition of others. Its core tenet is that every person has intrinsic worth and dignity (Ajitoni, 2024: 4). These principles encourage acts of kindness, empathy, and compassion towards others, reflecting the idea that one’s humanity is affirmed through relationship with others (Lefa, B., 2015). The well-being of one person, is seen as directly affecting the well-being of others, promoting a sense of solidarity and mutual responsibility. More to that, respect for one-self and others is fundamental value for Ubuntu philosophy. This entails honoring elders, valuing diverse perspectives, and treating everyone with dignity, regardless of their status or background (Mugumbate J, Nyanguru A, 2013). In addition to that, forgiveness, reconciliation, and the restoration of harmony are vital aspects of Ubuntu philosophy, as they promote the resolution of conflicts through dialogue and understanding, aiming to restore broken relationships and achieve social harmony (Lefa B, 2013). The notion of relationality-as part of the values of Ubuntu, can be interpreted in three levels i.e. as blood relations that everyone carries and each person’s responsibility within their family, communal relatedness and the last one is societal relations. These three levels of relationality are expressed in the Africans thrive for the value of relational collectivity, which attends to the moral and spiritual consciousness of what it means to be a human and to be in relationship with another and the environment

(Maphalala, 2017). For it is common for Africans to call each other brother or sister, uncle or auntie even though they do not have a blood relationship (Chilisa, 2012). In the African culture, human relations (family and communal) always come first, and the individual is often embedded in the family they come from, which often includes the extended family, the clan, and the tribe.

In practice, this relationality is manifested through caring and love for one another. This communal way of life encourages the development of society based on cooperative economics of sharing, not accumulating, of self-reliance, and independence (Maphalala, 2017). Love and connection underpin relationality and it is on the basis of love that people help and work together for the prosperity of the community, sharing and protecting each other from enemies. This is evidenced by the proverb from the Banyakitara people of the Western Uganda which states that, “Abangana tibakanya”, which literally translates as *those who hate each other cannot multiply or thrive or prosper*, espousing that a *community that eat together, grows together*. This proverb indicates that, being in relation with others is cherished, while being isolated is used as a high-level of punishment for the wrongdoers in the community.

Togetherness (*Ujoma*) and communal accountability (*Ujamaa*) are other important elements of the principles of Ubuntu. *Ujamaa* was promoted by Julius Kambarage Nyerere (1968), the first president of Tanzania, who conceived it as a cornerstone for the national development framework. For Nyerere, *Ujamaa* was more than an abstract philosophy; it was an operative principle that aimed to restructure Tanzania’s society along the lines of African family structures (Nyerere, 1968). His idea was to carve out a uniquely African path towards development, one that was entrenched in the shared values, traditions, and social structures of African societies (Nyerere, 1968). It propounds the belief that our humanity is mutually constitutive i.e. “I am human because I belong, I participate, I share” (Tutu, 2000:35).

Therefore, Ubuntu’s overreaching principles and values, emphasize the concept of “being a person” through others. That is, by being experienced and seen as human others, we become human. This embodiment of human-beingness is encapsulated in the loose

translation of Ubuntu that goes as “I am because we are (Mugumbate, Nyanguru, 2013) or “I am because you are and because you are, therefore I am.” This implies that, human individuality is necessary but not sufficient condition for being a person (Ramose, 2002: 65), an indication that, for Ubuntu philosophy, a person realizes oneself through relationship with others i.e. a person is a person because of others and thereby, through supporting others, a person enhances their life quality (Mayaka, Truell, 2021; Magumbate et al., 2023). It is from this context that in his *Collective Fingers’ Theory*, Mbigi (1997), emphasizes that Ubuntu philosophy is underpinned by social justice and human value of togetherness, solidarity, equity, compassion, and interdependence.

These values and principles from the Ubuntu philosophy, coincide with the Levinasian concept of ethics as the foundation of marriage according to which, “being-for-the-other”, takes precedence over and is better than being for-itself. Thus, the positive moment of Levinas’ thought lies in the moral transcendence of the Other person. Concomitantly, it lies in the moral response to transcendence, a self-charged with taking responsibility for the Other. Hence, the transcendence of the Other, becomes the central topic of “Totality and Infinity” while the “responsible self”, is taken as the central topic of “Otherwise than Being”. (Levinas, 2003: XXVI). This implies that, the humanism of the Other, is at the heart of Levinas’s ethics, since for him, the dignity of the self, arises in and as an unsurpassable moral responsibility to and for the Other person.

In addition to the notion of humanism, Levinas also delves into the relationship between ethics and justice, whereby according to him justice is the response to the ethical demands of the Other. The Other’s face calls us to respect them, to recognize their rights, and to treat them with dignity. Justice therefore, is not simply about enforcing laws or applying abstract principles, rather, it’s all about responding to the specific, unique as well as the demands of others. Justice requires us to go beyond the simplistic application of laws and to actively listen and respond to the needs of others. This suggests that according to Levinas, justice is not a passive acceptance of the existing systems, but an active engagement with the Other, an ongoing effort to ensure their well-being and recognition, i.e. it involves

an ongoing process of responding to the needs and demands of others, rather than simply adhering to a fixed set of rules or laws. (Levinas, 2023).

3. Cultural Contrast of the two Trends

It is obvious that the Ubuntu philosophical trend originates from the African cosmologies while Levinasian ethics draws its line of thought from Jewish theology as well as the Western philosophy. Despite the fact that the two trends originate from two differing cultures, interestingly, Ubuntu philosophy is also demonstrated by its counterparts in other culture(s), which is exemplified by integrating some views from Emmanuel Levinas, a Jewish-French existentialist and, agreeably, an ethical philosopher par excellence. This integration too, clarifies the significance of the Zulu maxim, wherein the concept of Other is epitomized by the “Face” or “Other”. Taking a cue from his philosophy, it is noted that his thought seems to resonate in the philosophy of Ubuntu. For he gives the impression that his own experience of the body of the Other (Pol-Droit, 2006: 2), also reflects the Bantu maxim, upholding humanity to Others, particularly in the assertion of the primacy of the Other (Burggraeve, 2002: XVII), wherein the notion of ethics becomes evident. For according to Levinas; ethics is not a reflexive activity but an experience. It does not result from a line of reasoning. It is not deduced but experienced. With the perception of the Other, each one finds oneself forced and obliged by the presence of the Other. For the philosopher, the central fact – of ethics but also of humanity as such, is to be found in the rapture brought about in the world by this bodily presence of the Other who imposes himself in a mode very different from things (Pol-Droit, 2006:2). This fact from the two philosophical thoughts, lead us into the point of complementarity.

4. Ubuntu and Levinas in Dialogue

One of the clearly observed fact from both, the Ubuntu philosophy and Levinasian ethics of responsibility, is the fact of acknowledging, concretizing and assigning a proper value and dignity to the human person. This is evidently showed by the details the two philosophical trends of reasoning provide on how intersubjectivity or human interactions and relationships ought to be established and operated. For Ubuntu which is a Zulu word that translates to “I am because we are”, is a

holistic worldview that sees all people as interconnected and interdependent. It teaches that we are all bound together by a common humanity, and that our well-being is inextricably linked to the well-being of others (Bello, 2025). Therefore, Ubuntu entails the comprehension of the human individual or the human person as an existential and simultaneously ethical being. Similarly, the notion of "Other" advocated by Levinas, is neither the inanimate object of our will, nor a thing, but the human Other. For in one's weakness and misery, the body of the Other not only shows that it is vulnerable but also inviolable i.e. it prohibits murder (Garcia, 2008:2). The experience of the presence of the Other calls for a recognition of the Other person, not superficially but concretely and sincerely. When Levinas calls this experience the "Face", he does not mean only literally the human face and its physical features. This fact is explained by Garcia that, the Face is not simply the human face but the entire body of the Other insofar as human, insofar as it directly addresses itself to me and bestows upon me a responsibility that I am not able by any means to cast away (Garcia, 2008:2).

This shows that what Levinas is advocating for, and what Ubuntu philosophy tries to convey, is all for the sake of humanity. This is an indication that understanding the ethical significance of seeing the Other, as a manifestation of an-Other self, and practicing it, draws the human being or culture out of egoism, complacency and indifference. (Garcia, 2008:2). So, the Zulu dictum in conjunction with the Levinasian ethics of responsibility, properly applied then, enables one to shun or turn away from selfish, egoistic, complacent and indifferent attitudes. For it enables the human person to feel responsible for the Other. This is clearly pointed out by Garcia as he quotes Levinas that, "It is my responsibility before a face looking at me as absolutely foreign that constitutes the original fact of fraternity" (Levinas, 1969: 215). In view of this "feeling responsible for the Other", the human person is driven to fundamentally understand oneself, so that in the process of recognizing the presence and affirming the primacy of the Other (the Face), one becomes ethical. For to become ethical, is to affirm the primacy of the Other.

5. Ethical Dimension of Ubuntu and its Implications for Contemporary Ethics.

The ethical dimension of Ubuntu philosophy, which is also conceived as an African philosophy for peace (Manda, 2009: 1ff), may be viewed from its notion of humanity to other, as it elicits some of its relevant implications. Similarly, it expresses some views on the Zulu maxim: "A person is a person through other persons". Correspondingly, this maxim illustrates the human person as existential and ethical. From this perspective then, the philosophy of Ubuntu continues to be given life in other cultures in different ways as it retains its existential-ethical characterizations, promoting and upholding humanity to others.

The African treatment of the human person, is not the result of the ruminations of any child on some magical things and experiences. Rather, it is an offshoot of the cogitations of the African people as existent human beings who partake of the capacity to think and reason (Giana, 2010:94). Applying the Cartesian cogito at this point, it is noted that the human person thinks therefore, he is, therefore he exists. The African thinks therefore, the African exists. This recognition is also true for non-Africans that think and reason. With this thought then, articulating the ethical dimension entails recognition of the fact that the Africans are not only existing, but also fundamentally thinking human beings (Louv, 1998: 1ff). Besides, their existence and way of thinking characterize their disposition towards their fellow humans, their being-with-others. It is an exposition of extending their humanity to others-human individuals and cultures that recognize, understand and accept them.

Moreover, this ethical dimension entails a sense of community and communality (Gianan, 2010: 86), which is reflected in the belief that the human person should not live in isolation of the Other (human person). This implies that every human person, should consider the value of the presence of the Other in community. In any case, Africans are of the view that a human being is only recognized as a human being through other human beings. In comparison with the Western notion of intersubjectivity, it should be noted that in traditional ethics, the self is often seen as an autonomous, rational agent who makes decisions based on moral principles. The self is the origin of action, and morality is something the self chooses or follows. Levinas however like the Ubuntu philosophy, offers a radically different conception of the selfhood whereby

the self is not the source of its own moral authority, rather, the self is defined by its responsibility to the Other. In other words, according to Levinas, the self does not find its identity through reflection, self-knowledge, or ontological understanding; instead, it is constituted through its response to the Other. i.e. the self becomes 'self' through the ethical engagement with the Other person. This implies that the moral responsibility towards Others, is not an additional obligation or a duty that we choose to take on, rather, it is what constitutes our very being as amoral subject.(Levinas, 2023). This indicates that, we affirm our humanity when we acknowledge that of Others (Manda, 2009: 1ff). According to this comprehension, the human being, is then, a human being because of the collective participation of Other human beings; hence, this relation, is also communal. Such that, if one is deprived of this collective participation, then, one becomes a "non-entity", hence it becomes a deprivation that illustrates an uncaring and dehumanizing way of thinking and behaving (Manda, 2009: 1ff). In contrast, it should be noted that the philosophy of Ubuntu actually promotes the principle of caring for the Other (Manda, 2009: 1ff, Mandela, 1994: 1ff).

In addition to that, the Ubuntu philosophy also aims at the full realization of others, the self-fulfillment of each human being, leading to the edification of the Other as an-Other self, i.e. as a process of self-realization through others (Louw, 1998: 1ff, Broodryk, 1997: 1ff). This implies that, without this aim advocated and fostered by Ubuntu philosophy, the human being becomes unethical. Although this does not immediately make one immoral, still there is a possibility to be such, in the process of acting or doing something. The act may become malicious, because one's action may no longer conform to the attainment of the aim-human beings' fullness of existence, one's full self-realization. This clearly shows that, upholding the ethical dimension of Ubuntu philosophy, can easily pave the way for peace. It should also be remembered that, embedded in this notion of peace, among others, are the personal, economic, axiological, cultural and environmental implications.

These implications, are derived from the fact that a human person cannot live in isolation of the other person. This indicates that, the Ubuntu philosophy

seeks to improve another person as oneself. For the "I am because we are", is given an intra-and inter-personal feature of human relationships. Hence, the personal implication entails one's harmonious relation with another human person (social), and one's relation with the government or the state (political). Thus, the Ubuntu philosophy instead of completion, espouses the idea that cooperation and participation can easily bring about better economic progress and prosperity. The axiological implication is expressed in the idea that it values the self and the Other (human person). It essentially sorts out the nature and type of the values of every human person regardless of colour, race, nationality, profession or status in life. The cultural implication is exemplified by the recognition and promotion of Ubuntu philosophy worldwide, involving other cultures, in the pursuit of edification of the human Other. The environmental implication is not to be ignored in the process, since the human-environment relationship has become so unstable and unpredictable. Climate change, for instance, is predominantly attributed to unhampered, indiscriminate tinkering of the natural environment by human beings themselves. With these few elucidated implications among others, the ethical dimension of Ubuntu philosophy also elicits the kind of responsibility that every human person possesses, and with which everyone can attain the plenitude of humanity to others.

Conclusion

The Ubuntu philosophy has been articulated in an attempt to promote the meaning of humanity to Others, which leads to the communication of its essential-ethical attributes. More so, it has been observed that upholding the Ubuntu philosophy fundamentally reinforces the maxim: "A person is a person through other persons," implying that the human person becomes a human person on account of other human persons. In delving into the ethical dimension of Ubuntu philosophy together with the Levinasian ethics of responsibility, the article has showed the pre-eminent role of every human person in promoting and upholding humanity to Others, realizing the good life-the accomplished human culture of life. This indicates that, once properly understood and carried out, both, the Ubuntu philosophy and the Levinasian ethics of responsibility, can lead to an ethical peace. For they put

meaning on the dialects of the self as an –Other. They promote cooperation and participation in the context of, for instance, pursuing economic prosperity. More to that, they promote the value of every human persons' end (axiological), not as means to a selfish/self-embellishing end. They uphold their own culture, while respecting and enriching other co-existing cultures. They seek to restore harmonious human environment relations. In their advocacy of the realization of humanity to others, Ubuntu philosophy and Levinasian ethics summon everyone to responsibly act towards the humanization and attainment of such ethical peace, that is with and for oneself, the Others and the world. Thus, the Levinasian ethics of responsibility together with the Ubuntu philosophy represent a radical rethinking of morality, one that places the encounter with the Other at the center of ethical thought. For Levinas, the ethical relationship is not about following rules or applying abstract principles, rather; it is about responding to the face of the Other, who calls us into an infinite responsibility. Such responsibility, is not a choice or a duty, but the very core of what it means to be human. Henceforth, being 'Called for the Other, encompasses responding to the Other's ethical needs responsibly in the daily face to face encounter.

References

- Ajitoni, B Deborah. "Ubuntu and the Philosophy of Community in African Thought: An Exploration of Collective Identity and Social Harmony" in *the Journal of African Studies and Sustainable Development*. Vol. 7, No.3, 2024.
- Aquino, Ranhilio. "The Dialectics of Power, Rights and Responsibility". *Kritike: An Online Journal of Philosophy*, 3:1, 2009: 1 – 9. Web.
- Burggrave, Roger. *The Wisdom of Love in the Service of Love: Emmanuel Levinas on Justice, Peace and Human Rights*. Trans., Jeffrey Bloech. Marquette: Marquette University, 2002.
- Blackburn, Simon. *Oxford Dictionary of Philosophy*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2005.
- Broodryk, John. *Ubuntu management and motivation*. Johannesburg: Gauteng Department of Welfare/Pretoria: Ubuntu School of Philosophy, 1997.
- Chilisa, Belege. "Indigenous Research Methodologies" Sage, in the *International Journal of Critical Indigenous Studies*, 2012.
- Dauenhauer, Bernard. "Paul Ricoeur". Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. 3 October 2005. Available at <http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/ricoeur/>. Web.
- Ewuoso Cornelius, Hall S. "Core Aspects of Ubuntu: A Systematic Review" in the *South African Journal of Bioethics and Law*. 12. 93, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.7196/SAJBL.2019.v12i2.679>.
- Fagunwa, Temitope. "Ubuntu: Revisiting an Endangered African Philosophy in Quest of a Pan Africanist Revolutionary Ideology" in the *Genealogy*. 3. 45, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genealogy3030045>.
- Fagenblat Michael, Erdur Melis eds., *Levinas and Analytic Philosophy, Second Person Normativity and the Moral Life*, New York: Routledge, 2020, 258.
- Garcia, Leovino. "Responsibility for the Other's Rights: Fraternity as Foundation for Equality and Freedom". In the UNESCO National Commission of the Philippines. 20 November 2008:1 – 8. <http://www.unesconatcom.ph/shs-papers.html>. Accessed on 4th March 2011.
- Levinas, Emmanuel. *Totality and Infinity: An Essay on Exteriority*, trans., Alphonso Lingis. Pittsburgh: Duquesne University Press, 1969.
- Levinas and the Ethical Responsibility Towards Others*, philosophy.institute/ethics/levinas-ethical-responsibility-towards-others/, accessed November 15, 2023.
- Levinas, Emmanuel. *Humanism of the Other*, trans., Nidra Poller Urbana & Chicago: University of Illinois Press, 2003, XXVI.
- Levinas and the Ethical Responsibility Towards Others*, available at philosophy.institute/ethics/levinas-ethical-responsibility-towards-others/, accessed on November 15, 2023.
- Lefa, Baken. "The African Philosophy of Ubuntu in South African Education" in the *Studies in Philosophy and Education*. 1. 15, 2015. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/274374017>.
- Louw, Dirk. "Ubuntu: An African Assessment of the Religious Other", *Paideia* (10 – 15 August 1998). <http://www.bu.edu/wcp/Papers/Afri/AfriLouw.htm>. Web.
- Mandela, Nelson. *A Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*. Boston: Little, Brown and Company, 1994.
- Mayaka, Bernard, Truell, Rory. "Ubuntu and its Potential Impact on the International Social

- Work Profession”, *International Social Work*, 64(5), 649–662, 2021.
- Maphalala, M. Christian. “Embracing Ubuntu in managing effective classrooms”, in *Gender and Behaviour*, 15(4), 10237–10249, 2017.
- Mugumbate, J, Nyanguru, A. “Exploring African philosophy: The Value of Ubuntu in Social Work” in the *African Journal of Social Work*, 3 (1), 82-100, 2013. [.https://ro.uow.edu.au/sspapers/3266](https://ro.uow.edu.au/sspapers/3266).
- Mugumbate J, Nyanguru, A. “Exploring African philosophy: The Value of Ubuntu in Social Work”, in the *African Journal of Social Work*, 10(1), 82–100, 2013.
- Msongana, N. Winnie. “The Significance of The Concept ‘Ubuntu’ for Educational Management And Leadership During Democratic Transformation In South Africa” in the *Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the University of Stellenbosch*, 83-113, 2006. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/37319167.pdf>
- Mbiti, J. S. *African Religions and Philosophy*, Nairobi: East African Educational Publishers Ltd, 1969.
- Mbigi, L. “Images of Ubuntu in global competitiveness” in the *Flying Springbok*, (4) 31–35, 1997
- Nyerere, Julius. “Ujamaa: The Basis of Socialism”, In *Ujamaa: Essays on Socialism*, (1–12), Dar Es Salaam, 1968.
- Pol-Droit, Roger. “The Other Above Everything”, trans., Leovino Garcia. *Le Monde*. France, 6 January 2006.
- Ramose, Mogobe. *The philosophy of Ubuntu as a philosophy*. Oxford University Press, 2002.
- Ricoeur, Paul. *Oneself as Another*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1992.
- Temples, Placid. *Bantu Philosophy*. Trans., Colin King. Paris: Presence Africaine, 1959.
- Van Breda, Adrian. “Developing the Notion of Ubuntu as African Theory for Social Work Practice” in the *Social Work* (55), 2019. <https://doi.org/10.15270/55-4-762>.
- Sanusi, Yekeen A, Spahn, Andreas. “Exploring Marginalization and Exclusion in Renewable Energy Development in Africa: A Perspective from Western Individualism and African Ubuntu Philosophy” In: Bombaerts, G., Jenkins, K., Sanusi, Y.A., Guoyu, W. (eds) *Energy Justice Across Borders*. Springer, Cham, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-24021-9_14.
- Soares, Conceição. “The Philosophy of Individualism: A Critical Perspective” in the *International Journal of Philosophy and Social Values*. 1, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.34632>.
- Samkange Stanlake, Samkange Thompson. *Hunhuism or Ubuntuism: A Zimbabwean Indigenous Political Philosophy*. Graham Publishing, 1980.
- Tutu, Desmond. *No Future Without Forgiveness: A Personal overview of South Africa’s Truth and Reconciliation Commission*. Rider Random House, 2000.
- Treanor, Brian. *Aspects of Alterity, Levinas, Marcel, and the Contemporary Debate* New York: Fordham University Press, 2006, 4.
- Woermann M, Engelbrecht, S. “The Ubuntu Challenge to Business: From Stakeholders to Relation Holders”, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 157(1), 27–44, 2019. <http://www.jstor.org>.